

Immersive Classroom with Augmented Reality: Cognitive Evaluation and Perceptions of Production Engineering Students in Assembly Assistance

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Abstract

This paper presents an interactive experience with an experimental augmented reality prototype for assisting in the assembly of parts in an academic environment. The research was carried out with students studying Information Systems in Production Engineering, who took part in practical tests using assembly assistance system based on augmented reality (AAS). During the activity, the students assembled a locomotive following the guidelines designed by the system, which used Deep Learning to recognize parts and detect hand movements. The experiment used three RGB cameras to capture the assembly process, allowing automatic analysis of the students' interactions with the system. Over the course of three lessons, the students were instructed to follow the assembly suggestions provided by the AAS. At the end, a questionnaire was applied to assess the cognitive load of the activity and understand the students' perception of the interaction with the experimental bench. The results indicated that the use of augmented reality helped them to understand the assembly steps and the association between process modeling notation and emerging technologies such as Deep Learning. In addition, the students provided feedback on challenges faced, such as improving the interface and increasing accuracy in detecting movements. This experience demonstrated the potential of immersive technologies in teaching and industry, highlighting how assembly assistance systems can not only enhance academic training, but also optimize industrial processes in the future.

Keywords: Assembly Assistance System; Skills.

1 Introduction

Technological advancements in recent years have significantly reshaped industrial processes through the integration of emerging technologies under the framework of Industry 4.0. Concepts such as artificial intelligence, the Internet of Things, augmented reality, and cyber-physical systems have revolutionized the way products are conceived, manufactured, and monitored across multiple industrial sectors (Schwab, 2016). This transformation demands a workforce equipped with advanced technological competencies and socio-technical skills that align with the complexities of modern production systems (Trevelyan, 2019).

However, higher education institutions, particularly those offering programs in engineering and technology, often struggle to match the rapid pace of industrial innovation (Trevelyan, 2019). Curricular frameworks and pedagogical practices remain, in many cases, anchored in traditional approaches that do not fully reflect the realities of contemporary engineering environments. Consequently, there is a pressing need to revise and modernize academic syllabi to incorporate practical experiences and technological tools that mirror those used in advanced industrial settings (Garcia Castro et al., 2024).

Among these tools, collaborative human-machine interaction systems represent a critical component of the current industrial paradigm. These systems, which facilitate seamless integration between human cognition and machine intelligence, are increasingly central to the operation of smart manufacturing environments (Trevelyan, 2019). Their inclusion in engineering education can serve as a bridge between theoretical knowledge and industrial application, fostering experiential learning and enhancing students' readiness for the workforce (Garcia Castro et al., 2024).

In response to this educational gap, a national prototype was developed through a collaborative project. The prototype features a reality-augmented assembly assistance system that integrates three RGB cameras, a LG projector, and a computational unit capable of real-time object and hand tracking.

The prototype projects visual guidance directly onto the workspace, supporting the user through successive stages of a predefined assembly process. A synthetic dataset, generated through data augmentation techniques, underpins the object recognition system, ensuring robust performance across variable conditions. This integration of hardware and software creates an immersive, feedback-oriented learning environment that emulates real-world manufacturing contexts (Romero et al., 2021).

The present study aims to evaluate students' perceptions of their interactions with the system during assembly activities conducted in an academic setting. By analyzing their feedback, the study seeks to assess the pedagogical potential of such assistive technologies and explore how they can be effectively incorporated into engineering curricula to better prepare students for the demands of Industry 4.0.

Therefore, this study is framed as an exploratory case study aiming to investigate the perceptions of Production Engineering students when interacting with a prototype under development of an augmented intelligence system for assembly assistance. The research seeks to understand how students evaluate the usability, cognitive load, and pedagogical potential of the technology in an educational setting, contributing to system refinement and to future applications in engineering learning environments.

2 Materials and Methods

This study is characterized as exploratory in nature, with the aim of analyzing student interaction with a national prototype of an assembly assistance system, developed at University in Brasília. The focus of the investigation was to understand students' perceptions and identify possible methodological improvements in the use of the prototype in practical learning contexts with Industry 4.0 technologies.

The purpose of the activity was to simulate for the students the dynamics of a real experiment, as typically conducted in the development of scientific research. In this way, the activity aimed to provide a practical and reflective experience, bringing students closer to the methodological steps involved in data collection and analysis, while fostering critical thinking and understanding of scientific investigation procedures.

The research was conducted with students regularly enrolled in the SIEP (Information Systems) course. The experiment took place in a laboratory environment, using an interactive augmented reality workbench capable of recognizing parts and identifying hand movements in real time.

The first methodological stage involved the presentation and signing of the Informed Consent Form (ICF), ensuring that the participants were aware of the objectives of the research, the use of the information and their freedom to participate. The students were then given an introductory explanation of how the bench worked, the objectives of the assembly and how to project the instructions. They then began to assemble a playful object - a little train - with parts recognized by the system from a database enriched with data augmentation

techniques. During the activity, the students followed instructions projected onto the workbench, which guided the order and correct positioning of the components.

After completing the assembly, the participants answered a structured questionnaire based on the instrument, which aims to measure the perceived workload in activities involving interaction with technological systems, considering dimensions such as mental effort, physical effort, time, perceived performance, frustration and overall task demand.

The data collected through the questionnaires was analyzed qualitatively and quantitatively, seeking to identify patterns of perception, strengths and limitations in the students' experience with the prototype. The results obtained contributed to reflection on teaching methodologies that incorporate emerging technologies, as well as improving the system as a teaching support tool in university environments.

2.1 Methodology for Analyzing the Student Experience

To assess the students' perception of the practical class experimenting with the augmented reality prototype, a digital form was used as a data collection tool. The main objective was to analyze the participants' experience of using the proposed technology.

In the first section of the form, the terms of welcome to the research were presented, including thanks for participating, the estimated time to complete the form, detailed instructions on how to answer the questions and information on the confidentiality of the data collected.

The second section aimed to collect the profile of the respondents. Information was collected on gender, age group, current occupation or previous professional experience, schooling, previous experience in assembly activities, familiarity with technologies in general, ability to concentrate, previous experience with augmented reality and the level of comfort in following written and visual instructions.

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In addition, the form included an assessment of the mental demand involved in carrying out the practical activity. Although the full index was not applied, the dimension related to cognitive effort was considered, including aspects such as perceived physical effort, concentration, reasoning, attention and thought load. The inclusion of this item was aimed at identifying the level of mental demand of the proposed task and providing input for future improvements to the prototype, as well as understanding the students' experience during interaction with augmented reality technology.

3 Innovations in Engineering Education

This section presents educational experiences that have used emerging technologies as a teaching tool, highlighting practices that involved direct experimentation by the students. Studies are discussed which demonstrate the results obtained through the application of active methodologies using resources such as augmented reality and interactive simulations.

Some authors point out that traditional teaching techniques no longer meet the demands of contemporary industry and that new teaching approaches are needed to promote greater alignment between academic training and the demands of the professional market (Leung et al., 2008; Romero et al., 2021; C. Zhang et al., 2025; X. Zhang et al., 2021). As demonstrated by Latifah et al. (2020), this expository format, still widely used in technical subjects, restricts opportunities for developing essential skills such as critical thinking, autonomy, collaboration, and the practical application of knowledge. These limitations reinforce the inadequacy of this

model in meeting the current demands of the industry and the challenges of engineering education, highlighting the need for more active and contextualized methodologies that promote student agency and integrate theory with practice.

In this context, the article analyzed proposes the integration of Design-Based Learning (DBL) and Outcome-Based Education (OBE) as an innovative methodology for teaching Industrial Engineering. This approach favors the development of systemic and critical thinking, problem-solving skills, teamwork, autonomy in learning and innovation among students. To investigate the effects of this methodological proposal, two practical experiments were carried out: the first involved a project applied to optimizing the storage and protection of metal parts in a company, focusing on the 5S tool; the second consisted of a comparative study between an experimental class, which used the DBL+OBE methodology, and a control class, subjected to traditional teaching. The didactic proposal emphasized student autonomy and active learning, as well as the practical application of theoretical content. Subsequent analysis of the experiences revealed that the students perceived the methodology as an opportunity to effectively integrate theory and practice, promoting greater engagement, collaborative work and direct contact with real industry problems, which contributed significantly to their professional training.

In the study carried out by Latifah et al. (2020), the Project-Based Learning (PBL) methodology was applied in technical engineering education, with the aim of comparing its effects in relation to the traditional expository model. The research involved two classes: an experimental class, which used PBL, and a control class, which was subjected to conventional teacher-centered teaching. The project was based on a real problem related to poor sanitation in the city of Garut, Indonesia, challenging students to develop solutions for the implementation of community septic tanks in densely populated areas. The use of educational technologies, such as simulation tools and computer-aided design, was integrated into the teaching process, helping to make the experience more contextualized and applied. The results indicated significant gains in the development of students' practical and interpersonal skills, while at the same time valuing the role of students in leading their own learning.

Another relevant case of success in the use of experimental practices in engineering education is presented by Zhang et al. (2025), who proposed an innovative practical lesson for teaching the wave-particle duality of light in Optics courses. The study showed that by using modern instruments such as optical fibers, three-dimensional optical traps and interferometry systems, students were able to simultaneously visualize the wave and corpuscular behavior of light - something that is difficult to understand in purely lecture-based classes. In addition, the students had the opportunity to develop practical skills relevant to the context of contemporary engineering, such as handling advanced optical equipment, interpreting experimental data and solving technical problems autonomously. These results highlight the importance of integrating educational technologies and active learning methodologies to train engineers who are better prepared for the challenges of today's market.

It is now increasingly common to develop applications and assistance systems based on deep learning algorithms to prevent errors in manual assembly processes in industrial environments (Gellert et al., 2020; Riedel et al., 2021). These systems play a key role not only in reducing operational failures, but also in improving operator training, both in manufacturing contexts and in academic environments.

4 Results of the Practical Educational Activity with Augmented Reality

The next two subsections present the results: Subsection 4.1 outlines the students' profiles and contextualizes their participation in the experiment, while Subsection 4.2 offers an individualized analysis of cognitive load levels and perceptions to assess the experiment's impact on learning.

4.1 Characterization of the Respondents and Structure of the Experimental Study

All respondents were higher education students. Among the eight participants, only one identified as female. The predominant age group was 18 to 24 years ($n = 7$), with only one participant falling into the 25 to 34 range.

Regarding familiarity with technology, five participants (62%) reported frequent use without advanced proficiency, while three (38%) indicated daily use of advanced technologies, suggesting high familiarity.

Figure 1. Participants' ability to concentrate

In terms of concentration capacity during task execution, three participants reported a moderate level, with occasional distractions; another three indicated low capacity for prolonged focus; and two described high ability to maintain concentration over extended periods (Figure 1).

Figure 2. Participants' experience with AR (augmented reality)

With respect to prior experience with augmented reality (AR) technologies, five participants stated they were only theoretically familiar, never having used the technology, while three reported having used it at least once (Figure 2).

Figure 3. Participants' comfort with instructions

And in relation to comfort in following written or visual instructions, six participants indicated feeling very comfortable, whereas two reported being moderately comfortable (Figure 3).

Figure 4. Mental Demand Assessment

Figure 4 shows the levels of mental demand perceived by the students during the activity with the augmented reality prototype. The classification was made on a scale of 1 to 5, with 1 indicating low demand and 5 extremely high demand. The most common rating observed was 3, given by four participants. This score suggests a moderately high perceived mental load, indicating that the students felt a significant but still manageable cognitive effort. Next, rating 2 was given by two participants, representing a lighter cognitive demand. Ratings 1 and 4 were chosen by one participant each. A total of eight students took part in the experiment, which confirms the total responses shown in the graph.

5 Conclusions

Based on the literature and the findings of this study, it can be concluded that the use of augmented reality significantly supported students in understanding the steps involved in assembly processes and in establishing connections between process modeling notation (BPMN) and emerging technologies such as Deep Learning. The feedback provided by students also revealed important challenges, particularly regarding interface improvements and the need for greater accuracy in movement detection. Overall, the experience confirmed

the educational and industrial potential of immersive technologies, demonstrating that assembly assistance systems not only enrich academic learning but also hold promise for enhancing efficiency and precision in industrial operations.

Furthermore, this study highlights the importance of offering engineering students not only theoretical exposure but also practical engagement with emerging technologies such as augmented reality—especially when these systems are still in development. Such experiences can empower students to apply these technologies in real-world industrial contexts and even inspire them to develop or adapt similar solutions in their future professional environments. Therefore, integrating interactive and experimental components into engineering curricula may contribute to fostering a new generation of professionals better prepared for the technological demands of Industry 4.0.

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